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Genes expressed in the mast cell are differentially methylated in ulcerative colitis.

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We used genomic methodologies to identify IBD-associated epigenetic changes through study of genome-wide methylation arrays. We describe the suggested importance of the mast cell program based on identification of three separate molecules that label or identify the mast cell: CD63, CD300a and KIT, as among those most differentially methylated in the genomic sequences of humans with ulcerative colitis. CD63, CD300a and KIT were expressed with tight regulation with a component of the high affinity IgE receptor in mast cells, *FCER1G*.